

EVALUATION OF THE SYSTEM AND ALGORITHM DEVELOPED FOR MOVING VEHICLES BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract. This study presents the development of a Deep Neural Network (DNN) model designed for an advanced vehicle monitoring and forecasting device. The model aims to identify moving vehicles by type and color with high accuracy. The architecture of the DNN includes two hidden layers, each comprising five neurons activated by the Sigmoid function, facilitating both forward and backward propagation processes for learning and prediction. The model employs a combination of appearance, motion, and updating algorithms for robust object tracking, integrating deep learning features with a visual attention mechanism to enhance vehicle detection accuracy and real-time performance. Additionally, the system incorporates a Compression and Motion Channel module to optimize feature extraction and processing. Evaluation of the model using standard datasets demonstrates significant improvements in tracking accuracy and processing speed compared to existing methods. The proposed algorithm exhibits a substantial enhancement in both real-time performance and accuracy, making it a viable solution for real-time multi-channel video analysis in intelligent transportation systems.

Keywords: Moving Vehicles, Deep Neural Network (DNN), feature extraction, Correlation Filter (CF), loss function, H filter, loss layer, error-free metrics, video-based vehicle monitoring, One-Pass Evaluation (OPE), Temporal Robustness Evaluation (TRE), and Spatial Robustness Evaluation (SRE), Overlap Ratio (OR).

Аннотация. В данном исследовании представлена разработка модели глубоких нейронных сетей (DNN), предназначенной для устройства мониторинга и прогнозирования, которое определяет движущиеся транспортные средства по типу и цвету с высокой точностью. Архитектура DNN включает два скрытых слоя, каждый из которых содержит пять нейронов, активируемых функцией Sigmoid, что позволяет выполнять процессы прямого и обратного распространения для обучения и предсказания. Модель использует комбинацию алгоритмов внешности, движения и обновления для надежного отслеживания объектов, интегрируя глубокие особенности обучения с визуальным механизмом внимания для повышения точности обнаружения транспортных средств и производительности в реальном времени. Кроме того, система включает модуль сжатия и канала движения для оптимизации извлечения и обработки признаков. Оценка модели с использованием стандартных наборов данных демонстрирует значительные улучшения в точности отслеживания и скорости обработки по сравнению с существующими методами. Предложенный алгоритм показывает значительное улучшение как в производительности в реальном времени, так и в точности, что делает его жизнеспособным решением для анализа видео в реальном времени в интеллектуальных транспортных системах.

Introduction

A deep neural network (DNN) model has been developed for a device that monitors and forecasts error-free metrics for identifying moving vehicles by type and color. As illustrated in Figure 1, the method based on the Deep Neural Network (DNN) model comprises four inputs and two outputs. This model consists of two hidden layers. In neural networks, there exists a hidden layer between the input and output, which enhances the focus on the data and controls the output signal through an activation function. The functionality of hidden layers varies depending on the performance of the neural network and may differ according to the stresses associated with similar layers. The first hidden layer consists of five neurons based on the Sigmoid activation function. Similarly, the second hidden layer also comprises five neurons based on the Sigmoid activation function.

Figure 1. Detection and Monitoring of Moving Vehicles

The DNN-based model executes a series of processes, including result acquisition and training involving forward and backward propagation. The result acquisition process can be observed in Figure 4.

$$out_{1,j} = x_j \quad (1)$$

$$fact_1 = fact_2 = fact_3 = \sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}} \quad (2)$$

$$out_{2,k} = fact_1([\sum_{j=1}^4 out_{1,j} \cdot w_{1,j,k}] + b_{1,k}) = fact_1([\sum_{j=1}^4 x_j \cdot w_{1,j,k}] + b_{1,k}) \quad (3)$$

$$out_{3,m} = fact_2([\sum_{k=1}^5 out_{2,k} \cdot w_{2,k,m}] + b_{2,m}) \quad (4)$$

$$y_n = fact_3([\sum_{m=1}^5 out_{3,m} \cdot w_{3,m,n}] + b_{3,n}) \quad (5)$$

or

$$y_n = fact_3([\sum_{m=1}^5 fact_2([\sum_{k=1}^5 fact_1([\sum_{j=1}^4 x_j \cdot w_{1,j,k}] + b_{1,k}) \cdot w_{2,k,m}] + b_{2,m}) \cdot w_{3,m,n}] + b_{3,n}) \quad (6)$$

$$y_n = fact_3([\sum_{m=1}^5 fact_2([\sum_{k=1}^5 fact_1([\sum_{j=1}^4 x_j \cdot w_{1,j,k}] + b_{1,k}) \cdot w_{2,k,m}] + b_{2,m}) \cdot w_{3,m,n}] + b_{3,n}) \quad (7)$$

$$y_n = \left[1 + e^{-\left(\sum_{m=1}^5 \frac{w_{3,m,n}}{1 + e^{-\left(\sum_{k=1}^5 \frac{w_{2,k,m}}{1 + e^{-\left(\sum_{j=1}^4 x_j \cdot w_{1,j,k} + b_{1,k} \right)}} + b_{2,m} \right)}} + b_{3,n} \right)} \right]^{-1} \quad (8)$$

The training process of the Deep Neural Network (DNN) model for the device developed to monitor and forecast the detection metrics of moving vehicles by color and type is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Training process of the Deep Neural Network (DNN) model for the device developed to monitor and forecast detection metrics of moving vehicles by color and type.

$$grad_{3,n} = (target_n - y_n) \cdot \frac{dfact3(y_n)}{dy_n} \quad (9)$$

$$grad_{2,m} = \left(\sum_{n=1}^2 w_{3,m,n} \cdot grad_{3,n} \right) \cdot \frac{dfact2(out_{3,m})}{dout_{3,m}} \quad (10)$$

$$grad_{1,k} = \left(\sum_{m=1}^5 w_{2,k,m} \cdot grad_{2,m} \right) \cdot \frac{dfact1(out_{2,k})}{dout_{2,k}} \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \sigma(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{1}{1+e^{-x}} \right] = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}} \right) = \sigma(x)[1 - \sigma(x)] \quad (12)$$

Back propagation: The process of updating the stress parameters in the Deep Neural Network (DNN) model for the device developed to monitor and forecast detection metrics of moving vehicles by color and type.

$$\Delta w_{3,m,n} = eta \cdot out_{3,m} \cdot grad_{3m} + alpha \cdot old \Delta w_{3,m,n} \quad (13)$$

$$w_{3,m,n} = old w_{3,m,n} + \Delta w_{3,m,n} \quad (14)$$

and $old \Delta w_{2,k,m}^{(15)} = \Delta w_{2,k,m} \quad old w_{2,k,m} = w_{2,k,m}$

$$\Delta w_{2,k,m} = eta \cdot out_{2,k} \cdot grad_{2,k} + alpha \cdot old \Delta w_{2,k,m} \quad (16)$$

$$w_{2,k,m} = old w_{2,k,m} + \Delta w_{2,k,m} \quad (17)$$

$$old \Delta w_{1,j,k} = \Delta w_{1,j,k} \quad (18)$$

$$\Delta w_{1,j,k} = eta \cdot out_{1,j} \cdot grad_{1,j} + alpha \cdot old \Delta w_{1,j,k} \quad (19)$$

$$w_{1,j,k} = old w_{1,j,k} + \Delta w_{1,j,k} \quad (20)$$

This method of an information system for the history of moving vehicles based on artificial intelligence comprises three components based on deep features for tracking the Correlation Filter (CF) object: the appearance model, the motion model, and the updating model. The appearance model, i.e., the object tracking algorithms, can be divided into two types: generative and discriminative models. Discriminative models usually demonstrate higher tracking effectiveness compared to generative models [1]. The CF algorithm periodically modifies its features (for example, the white color and light vehicle type, Chevrolet Lacetti brand) to generate positive and negative samples for learning the H filter [2].

$$g_i = f_i * h \quad (21)$$

Thus, the correlation data direction is obtained. The location of the object is identified at the point where the correlation direction has the maximum value [3, 4, 5]. The network structure design shown in Figure 1 of this research has been developed, indicating the structure of the direction network. This network structure is divided into three parts; namely, the feature extraction network, the CF layer response loss layer, and the feature extraction network. The lower network of the feature extraction network is a sector where the object's location is unknown, allowing for the exploration of how to search in the next frame once known.

Figure 4. The process of Response L2 Loss.

In applying deep learning for feature extraction, two main problems were addressed: (1) A suitable feature specific to a given task was identified, and the network structure was designed accordingly. (2) A loss function was designed to optimize the network based on the parameters of the vehicle. The feature extraction process in deep convolutional networks demonstrates that shallow networks strive to capture the object's boundaries, shape, contours, color, and structure. Significant size variations in detecting moving vehicles occur when a vehicle moves from far to near or vice versa. An increase in the number of network layers leads to a significant computational impact and affects the application in real time. Consequently, a feature extraction network was developed, as these networks facilitate easier learning of object features (for example, shape, contours, color, type, and model), making the training process more stable.

Figure 4. Initial module of the vehicle tracking algorithm integrating the detector and observer device.

Due to the time-consuming nature of searching for vehicles in all areas of the field of view during the video-based vehicle monitoring process, a visual attention mechanism was incorporated into the feature extraction network in the research to enhance sensitivity for comprehensive vehicle visibility and monitoring. This approach allowed for the suppression of background features in the feature extraction network and enhanced the network's efficiency in reflecting vehicle

characteristics, thereby improving the accuracy and speed of vehicle detection and monitoring. The main channel module, as shown in Figure 5, has been integrated into the output of each layer [6].

Figure 5. Schematic of the main module of the compression and motion channel.

This module consists of three components: compression, motion, and scaling processes. Here, after the convolution process for input x with feature channels $c1$, a location with feature size $c2$ is output. The compression process through collective pooling transforms each 2D feature channel into a real number covering the receptive field and produces a one-dimensional vector corresponding to the size of the feature location. This vector describes the distribution of responses in the feature channel and allows for a receptive field in layers close to the input layer.

In the CF and response loss layers, if the dimensions of the previous input in the network are $M \times N$ for the image block, then the feature $ph(x) \in RM \times N \times D$ for the image block is obtained through the feature extraction network. Positive and negative samples are periodically generated through shifting, and used in training the w filter, which can be achieved using the minimization equation (equation (21)):

$$\min_{\omega} \|X_{\omega} - y\|_2^2 + \lambda \|\omega\|_2^2 \quad (22)$$

Here: ($\lambda \geq 0$) is the regularization coefficient, and $X = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]^T$ is the data matrix consisting of all positive and negative samples resulting from the feature. The closed-form solution of the equation (22) was calculated using the least squares method [168].

$$\omega = (X^T X + \lambda I)^{-1} X^T y \quad (23)$$

The above equation can be rewritten in the field of complex numbers as follows:

$$\omega = (X^H X + \lambda I)^{-1} X^H y \quad (24)$$

X is a circulant matrix. Therefore, $l - (l \in \{1, \dots, D\})$ in the feature channel is written in the form of a filter equation (24):

$$\hat{\omega}_l = \frac{\hat{y} \odot x_l^*}{\sum_{i=1}^D x_i^* \odot x_{i+l}} \quad (25)$$

The image block z being searched in the current branch and the image block x have the same dimensions. The feature z for the image block z is obtained through the feature extraction network, and the response R of the filter can be calculated using equation (25).

$$R = F^{-1}(\sum_{l=1}^D \hat{\omega}_l \odot \hat{\varphi}(z)_l^*) \quad (26)$$

The loss function of the network was defined as the L2 norm between the response R and the label, aligned at the peak of the 2D Gaussian function's center. This is shown in equation (26).

$$L(\theta) = \|R - \hat{R}\|^2 + \|\theta\|^2$$

$$s.t \ R = F^{-1}(\sum_{l=1}^D \hat{\omega}_l^* \odot \hat{\varphi}_l(z, \theta)) \quad (27)$$

$$\hat{\omega}_i = \frac{\hat{y}^* \odot \hat{\varphi}_i(x, \theta)}{\sum_{i=1}^D \hat{\varphi}_i(x, \theta) \odot (\hat{\varphi}_i(x, \theta))^* + \lambda}$$

As indicated in this equation, it can be derived using the chain rule (27) (for detailed information, see [167]).

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \varphi_l(z)} = F^{-1} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial (\hat{\varphi}_l(x))^*} + \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial (\hat{\varphi}_l(x))} \right)^* \right),$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \varphi_l(z)} = F^{-1} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial (\hat{\varphi}_l(z))^*} \right) \quad (28)$$

During the process of object tracking with online updating and scaling adaptation, there were changes in the sequence of images and the general orientation of the object. Additionally, the background where the object was located also changed over time. To achieve accurate and stable object tracking, an online update strategy and adaptation to background changes were necessary. Figure 6 shows the online tracking process of the object tracker integrated with the deep network and CF. In this search area, deep features are placed and input into the filter for the response.

Figure 6. Framework of the tracker integrated with the deep network and CF.

In the tracking flow shown in Figure 6, the state of the object can be observed. If the object shrinks, the filter learns a large amount of background information, and conversely, if the object expands, the filter shifts with the local texture of the object. The general flow of the tracking algorithm in the artificial intelligence-based information system for the history of moving vehicles was described as follows:

1. The deep neural features of the object were extracted based on the tracking region of the frames in the video sequence, and CF was initiated.
2. For each subsequent image in the video sequence, an image pyramid is established based on the predicted object region. Equation (28) shows the pyramid scaling factor.
3. The formula is shown as follows:

$$\left\{ a^s \mid s = \left\lfloor -\frac{s-1}{2} \right\rfloor, \left\lfloor -\frac{s-3}{2} \right\rfloor, \dots, \left\lfloor \frac{s-1}{2} \right\rfloor \right\} \quad (29)$$

Using the feature extraction network, a multi-scale feature direction can be obtained. Each feature direction at each scale is processed and allowed to respond to the CF. The location of the maximum value in each response indicates the object's position, and the corresponding scale is calculated as the scaling ratio for the object in the current frame. Equation (29) demonstrates the new methods of applying the filter. This update was carried out to sufficiently utilize the integrated data presented in the video sequence, improve the robustness of the filter to withstand external noise factors, and enhance the filter's stability.

$$W = \eta^W + (1 - \eta)A_i \quad (30)$$

Here is represented the learning efficiency, and the computational results for the current frame. By integrating devices with a detector, the initial position of the object in tracking is ensured, and an automatic tracking solution is explored. This solution addresses the dynamic changes in automatically detecting newly identified vehicles based on the detector and solves the issue of previously detected vehicles disappearing during the monitoring process. Tracking and comparison were used to predict the positions of objects in the frame. Values close to the predicted values were sought. Additionally, to correct the predicted values, the relationships among position, movement direction, and historical features were re-tracked to select the appropriate values. Studies have shown that the proposed solution and its algorithm provide sufficient results and can re-track the objects of interest within a short time. Figure 7 shows the flowchart of the object tracking algorithm developed in this research, which mainly consists of two parts: adapting the tracked and predicted values and correcting the predicted values; finding the objects of interest and new objects within the shortest time interval.

Figure 7. Flowchart of the object tracking algorithm by integrating devices with the detector.

Basically, evaluating the tracking quality involves predicting the movement of the CF object in real-time based on its previous position. In road traffic monitoring, loss of the object due to mutual occlusion occurred. Therefore, in this study, methods for calculating the tracking quality using the PSR equation were employed (equation (30)) [8].

$$PSR = \frac{g_{max} - \mu_{s1}}{\sigma_{s1}} \quad (31)$$

Here g_{max} is the maximum value of the CF response direction;

μ_{s1} and σ_{s1} are the mean and standard deviation of $N \times N$, respectively.

In this study, N was set to 12. The test analyses and data results indicated that PSR ranged from 5 to 10 in normal tracking conditions. When $PSR < 5$, it can be determined that tracking drift or loss has occurred. The distance d from the detection region boundary in the direction of the object's movement can be calculated. When $d < D$ (where D is the distance between the object and the boundary), values that do not match the tracked values in several consecutive frames are discarded. The predicted and tracked object values are relatively close in spatial distance; thus, for streets with relatively low traffic density, it was sufficient to adapt the tracked values according to spatial constraints.

However, as shown in Figure 8, for areas with relatively high traffic density and objects that occlude each other, spatial constraints alone may not be easily applicable. Taking this issue into

account, the study adapted the tracked and predicted values using a combination of spatial constraints and filtering. The spatial constraint is as follows:

$$IOU(r_d, r_p) = \frac{r_d \cap r_p}{r_d \cup r_d} > th \quad (32)$$

Figure 8. Diagram illustrating the matching of tracked and predicted object values.

If the tracked values, IOU, and predicted values are greater than the threshold th , they are selected as corresponding candidates. Extracting objects close to the predicted values significantly reduces the search area and increases processing efficiency. In this study, th was set to 0.2.

To correct the predicted value, the highest response value corresponding to the accurately predicted and tracked value is selected, as the highest response value represents the confidence in the predicted object.

$$r = \begin{cases} r_d & \text{if } g_{rd} \geq g_{rp} \\ r_p & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

Here is the final result, the predicted value and the tracked value.

In a confined area, for tracking new objects that do not match the tracked values or for re-tracking new objects entering the field of view or objects not registered in the STSS list, the following conditions were initially checked in a temporary linked list:

1. The object in the temporary linked list is located in a circular region with the tracked value as the center and radius RRR.
2. In a traffic scenario, an object does not abruptly change its direction in a short period. The reappearance location of the tracked value should be ahead of the moving direction of the object in the temporary linked list. To address the boundary issue, let $p(xi, yi)$ be the current location of the object center. The distance di ($i = 0, 1, 2$ va 3) from the object to the image boundary can be easily calculated. If $\min(\{di, i = 0, 1, 2, 3\}) > dist$ the object has fully entered the monitoring area. In such a case, the tracker for this object is activated. In this study, th was set to 6.0 for re-tracking occluded objects.

In the experimental parameters and dataset, the experiment was conducted on a computer with the Windows 10 operating system, an Intel Core i7-7700 K quad-core processor, 8 GB of RAM, an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 graphics card, and 8 GB of video memory. The video object detection dataset from the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge 2023 was used as the experimental training dataset. Additionally, studies were conducted based on the data from.

Table 1.

Table 1. Evaluation Metrics Dataset

No	Parameters and Dataset	Value
1	Training dataset	937

2	Validation dataset	555
3	Length of training sequences	56 - 458 frames
4	Number of sample pairs	2.5 times larger
5	Sample input size	75 x 75
6	Batch size	50
7	Momentum	0.9
8	Weight decay coefficient	0.005
9	Learning rate coefficient	0.00001
10	Epochs	20
11	Number of CF scale pyramids	3
12	Scale coefficient	1.0275
13	Testing platform	OTB2013 and OTB2015
14	Test dataset	100

To evaluate the performance of the tracking algorithm for identifying moving vehicles by type and color, three indices were used: One-Pass Evaluation (OPE), Temporal Robustness Evaluation (TRE), and Spatial Robustness Evaluation (SRE). In the quantitative analysis of these indices' robustness, mean accuracy and success plots were employed.

The success plot is generated by varying the overlap ratio. The area under the success curve (AUC) can more comprehensively reflect the tracker's performance. The Overlap Ratio (OR) is defined as the ratio of the intersection area between the predicted and the actual bounding boxes to the union area between the predicted and actual bounding boxes.

$$OR = \frac{|r_p \cap r_g|}{|r_p \cup r_g|} \quad (34)$$

Here, r_p and r_g are the predicted and actual bounding boxes, respectively.

One-Pass Evaluation (OPE) was used to assess tracking efficiency. Specifically, only the first frame was initialized, and then the mean accuracy and success were calculated using the aforementioned methods. The Online Tracking Benchmark (OTB) datasets from 2023 and 2024 were selected. These two datasets include a total of 100 video sequences containing 11 challenging problems in the field of visual tracking, such as scale variation, rapid motion, and motion blur. The OTB standard test platform was used for the evaluation.

a) OTB 2023 Dataset

b) OTB 2024 Dataset

Figure 9. The average success and accuracy curve OPE results of the two types of algorithms are shown in the provided images a) OTB 2023 Dataset and b) OTB 2024 Dataset.

Experimental results indicate that the model developed in this research achieved accuracy comparable to deep network - CF-combined trackers (e.g., HCF [9] and DCFNet [10]). Due to the deep network structure or high dimensionality, these algorithms have relatively low processing speeds but relatively high tracking accuracy and are preferred over CF trackers (e.g., Circulant Structure Kernel (CSK), KCF [11], Discriminative Scale Space Tracker (DSST)).

TRE involves randomly selecting a total of 100 frames as the initial frame from each test sequence, providing the average accuracy and average success rate of various tracking algorithms. As shown in Figure 9, for the OTB 2023 dataset, the methods proposed in this paper rank first among the listed comparison methods in terms of average success rate curve and average accuracy.

a) OTB 2023 Dataset

b) OTB 2024 Dataset

Figure 10. The average success and accuracy curve TRE results of the two types of algorithms are shown in the provided images a) OTB 2023 Dataset and b) OTB 2024 Dataset.

For SRE, the position and size of the initial target box for each test sequence were varied according to the ground truth. During the process of setting the positional offset, a rectangular area with a size 10% of the target size was constructed with the center of the ground truth as its center, and

the spatial position was randomly selected within an area with a random frequency of 20% of the area size.

a) OTB 2023 Dataset

b) OTB 2024 Dataset

Figure 11. The average success and accuracy curve SRE results of the two types of algorithms are shown in the provided images a) OTB 2023 Dataset and b) OTB 2024 Dataset.

During the scale variation setting process, the scale change must be 0.8, 0.9, 1.1, and 1.2 times the actual values. As shown in Figure 10, for the OTB2013 dataset, if the Overlap Ratio (OR) is less than 0.4, the average success rate of the algorithm in this paper is equal to that of DCF Net and ranks second only to HCF. If the OR is greater than 0.4, the average success rate of the algorithm in this paper exceeds the speed of other algorithms. In terms of average accuracy, if the positioning error threshold is less than 19, the performance of the algorithm in this paper demonstrates absolute superiority.

Real-time performance of the algorithm: The main objective of this research was to present a vehicle tracking algorithm suitable for real-time multi-channel video analysis in an intelligent transportation system. The real-time performance of the algorithm is of crucial importance. Timely execution of object tracking, as an essential part of a real-time monitoring system, is vital. Table 2 summarizes the comparison of processing speeds for seven trackers. The relative speed-up rate of the proposed algorithm is 150% compared to the original DCFNet algorithm, and the speed of the proposed algorithm is nearly 14 times faster than the HCF algorithm.

To comprehensively evaluate the timeliness and tracking accuracy indices of tracking algorithms, a real-time multi-channel video analysis application is used as an example for comparison. If the real-time video processing requirement for each channel is 24 FPS, an average processing speed above 96 FPS is required for real-time video analysis of four or more channels. The test results in Table 2 indicate that three algorithms meet this requirement: CSK, KCF, and the proposed algorithm. The tracking accuracy indices shown in Figures 7, 8, and 9 indicate that the algorithm proposed in this study outperforms the other two algorithms.

Table 2.

We achieved a significant improvement of 6.5% mAP compared to Faster R-CNN and 6.9% compared to SSD300.

Models	Overall (mAP)	Car	Bus	Minibus	Truck
Fast R-CNN	67.2	53.6	83.2	62.5	69.5
Faster R-CNN	69.2	55.2	85.4	64.7	71.3
YOLO	58.9	46.6	75.2	53.4	60.5
SSD300	68.8	54.4	85.1	64.3	71.5
SSD512	71.2	57.4	87.2	66.8	73.4
RON320 [25]	73.6	60.2	89.5	69.1	75.5
Ours	75.7	62.4	91.8	71.3	77.3

To evaluate the efficiency of the proposed network, it was compared with state-of-the-art detectors on the JSHD. The results of our experiments are presented in Table 3. A significant improvement of 6.5% mAP compared to the state-of-the-art Faster R-CNN and 6.9% compared to SSD300 was achieved. The developed network demonstrated strong capability in detecting vehicles with widely varying scales, particularly for small vehicles. In testing, the network's speed reached 15 FPS, which is three times faster than Faster R-CNN.

Additionally, the network base consists of Faster R-CNN and SSD. To improve detection, k-means, feature fusion, and detection in various functions were used to enhance the baseline, and the analysis results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3.

Qualitative evaluations for our approach on the test set.

	Faster R-CNN				Ours
<i>k</i> -means?		√	√	√	√
Feature concatenate?			√	√	√
Detecting on different feature?				√	√
Batch normalization?					√
JSHD (mAP)	69.2	70.8	72.8	73.8	75.7

Conclusion

In this study, along with tracking vehicles in traffic scenes, an object tracking algorithm was selected as the integrated object tracker and detector. A CF tracker based on deep features was developed for the tracking device, and the tracker was primarily used to predict the object's location in the next frame for tracker-detector integration. The tracking quality was evaluated based on PSR. For vehicles with relatively low tracking quality or those whose tracked values did not match over several consecutive frames, spatial location constraints were applied to correct the predicted locations. Experimental results showed that the proposed multi-object tracking algorithm is capable of stable and continuous tracking of objects in traffic scenes and re-tracking occluded objects.

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